

Direct Spectrophotometric Determination of Nickel with 3-Hydroxy-3-n-propyl-1-p-tolyltriazene

REKHA BHATT, B. REZAIIE, A. K. GOSWAMI, R. S. CHAUHAN and D. N. PUROHIT*

Department of Chemistry, M. L. Sukhadia University, Udaipur-313 001

Manuscript received 17 May 1994, accepted 11 July 1994

3-Hydroxy-3-n-propyl-1-p-tolyltriazene (HPTT) was synthesised earlier^{1,2}. The present communication deals with the spectrophotometric determination of nickel with this reagent.

Results and Discussion

The reagent HPTT forms an ethanol-soluble greenish yellow complex with nickel in the pH range 7.8–8.2. The complex exhibited $\lambda_{\max}$ at 360 nm and the working wavelength was kept at 370 nm. Full colour developed immediately and remained stable. Maximum colour was developed with eight-fold excess of the reagent.

Job's method, slope-ratio method and mole-ratio methods of Yoe and Jones³ and of Zolotov⁴ established the composition of complex Ni : R as 1 : 3. Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range 0.58–3.52 ppm. Molar absorptivity value was found to be $7.417 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and Sandell's sensitivity 7.91 ng cm^{-2} . Standard deviation using 2.93 ppm of nickel was found as 0.02 ppm from precision studies (10 determinations). The conditional stability constant was found using Harvey and Manning's curve as $\log \beta = 15.71$.

The interference studies revealed that 2.93 ppm of nickel could be determined in presence of 5 ppm of Na^+ , K^+ , Ag^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , F^- , Cl^- , Br^- ,

I^- , NO_3^- , CH_3COO^- , CO_3^{2-} , SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} . Further, 5 ppm of Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , oxalate and molybdate were found to interfere.

The solid complex was crystallised from ethanol to obtain greenish yellow crystals, m.p. 45°. The elemental analysis of the complex accounted for the molecular formula $\text{NiC}_{30}\text{H}_{43}\text{N}_9\text{O}_3$.

Experimental

The reagent HPTT was prepared by the reported method¹; its $1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ solution was prepared in ethanol.

A solution of $1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ of Ni^{2+} was prepared by dissolving the requisite amount of $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (AnalaR) in water, and standardised with EDTA at pH 7.8–8.2 using murexide as indicator. Weaker solutions were prepared by appropriate dilution. A 1% aqueous buffer and a 1% ethanolic perchloric acid were used to adjust the desired pH. A Systronics 108 spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurement and a Systronics 324 pH meter used for pH measurement.

References

1. D. N. PUROHIT, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1973, **66**, 468.
2. D. N. PUROHIT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 710.
3. Y. H. YOE and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.
4. YU. A. ZOLOTOV, "Extraction of Chelating Compounds", Ann Arbor, 1970.

